

Thoughts on the development of cultural tourism industry under the background of normalization of epidemic prevention and control

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Abstract: The full outbreak of the COVID-19 in 2020 has plunged the global tourism industry into temporary difficulties. After the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, the development of the tourism industry is facing new problems. How to effectively reform and innovate the tourism industry to adapt to the post epidemic era has become an important topic of public concern. Taking the development of cultural tourism industry as the research object, the normalization of epidemic prevention and control as the background, and China's cultural tourism industry as an example, this paper analyzes the problems encountered in the development of cultural tourism industry, and puts forward suggestions and measures in combination with the actual situation, so as to improve the development capacity of cultural tourism industry under the normalization of epidemic prevention and control.

Keywords: Epidemic Normalization; Culture And Tourism; Cultural Tourism Industry.

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Accepted: 27 June, 2022; **Published:** 7 July, 2022

How to cite this article: Bat-ulzii Tsendsuren (2022). Thoughts on the development of cultural tourism industry under the background of normalization of epidemic prevention and control. *North American Academic Research*, 5(6), 161-169. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6800126>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

In the era of low-carbon economy, the two major industries of culture and tourism have gradually become the "green sunrise industry" that major countries in the world give priority to. As early as 2018, China proposed to "promote the integrated development of cultural industry and tourism, sports, information, logistics, construction and other industries". As a new model of the tertiary industry that China vigorously supports, the integrated development of the two major industries of culture and tourism is of great significance to promote the development, upgrading and structural transformation of the entire national economy. The project and purpose of tourism determine its cultural content. Therefore, the combination of culture and tourism presents a new model for the development of China's tourism industry under the background of the new era. However, under the influence of the COVID-19 in 2020, the global tourism industry has suffered a major impact, and the vulnerability of the cultural tourism industry has been fully exposed. In the past few years, the slow recovery of the cultural and tourism industry, the reduction of the

industrial scale, the cautious flow of market funds and other issues have gradually become prominent, which has also led to the gradual reduction of the proportion of tourism consumption, the narrowing of the scope of tourism, and the increasing psychological pressure on tourism. At the same time, in the cultural and tourism industry, enterprises have also experienced problems such as the reduction of the degree of specialization, the slowdown in the trend of innovative cultural and tourism models, and the brain drain of the cultural and tourism industry. With the normalization of the epidemic situation, the future development of the cultural tourism industry must comply with the new requirements of the times and follow the trend.

Research Methodology

1. Development status and trend of China's cultural tourism industry

(1) The structure of cultural tourism industry has changed: youth has become the main trend.

As China's tourism industry has maintained a high growth rate for many years, the structure of the tourism industry has also changed. According to the statistical data in the analysis report on the market prospect and investment strategic planning of China's tourism industry, in terms of travel purpose and travel mode, leisure tourism has replaced sightseeing tourism as the main travel purpose, and the popularity of parent-child travel market has been increasing; In terms of the structure of travel groups, youth has become the main trend. Users under the age of 35 are the main group of tourism users. The proportion of female users has also gradually increased, and the proportion of men and women has developed more evenly; In terms of destinations and popular tourist destination cities, economically developed provinces are more popular. The construction of tourist facilities, cultural environment and food culture of destination cities are all factors considered by tourist groups. Among them, the most important part, the cultural tourism industry market, is gradually becoming the "new favorite" of China's tourism industry at this stage. According to the statistical data of 2021, despite the impact of the epidemic, China's cultural and tourism industry still maintains a good trend. The most obvious feature is that the cultural and tourism industry is gradually changing in structure. The huge tourism group composed of young people has gradually become concentrated in the cultural and tourism industry, with theme amusement, scenic spot support Tourism projects such as cultural tourism town type and resort hotel type provide a new modern tourism model for young people, and indirectly make China's tourism industry affected by the epidemic gradually improve.

(2) In the future, the total revenue of China's cultural tourism industry will exceed 3trillion yuan.

On the one hand, with the continuous improvement of residents' consumption level and the continuous development of cultural tourism construction, China's tourism industry is in a vigorous development stage. On the other hand, different epidemic prevention policies in different parts of China have different impacts on the tourism industry. Therefore, more attention should be paid to the correlation between the orientation of the tourism industry and the epidemic prevention policies in the trend of the continuous expansion of the scale of tourists and the continuous increase of the proportion of people who have traveled many times during the year. Although more and more people choose cultural tourism, and continue to promote the scale of China's cultural tourism industry in the tourism industry, according to the statistical data of the analysis report on China's tourism industry market prospect and investment strategic planning released by the prospective industry research institute, the total revenue of China's tourism industry in 2012 only reached 2.58 trillion yuan, and in 2013 the total revenue of China's tourism industry exceeded 4 trillion yuan. In 2018, the tourism industry followed the government's policy guidance, launched the culture tourism integration industry, added cultural connotation to tourist attractions, expanded the space for tourism economic development with culture, and promoted the development of quality tourism with supply side reform. While continuously enhancing people's sense of tourism, the total domestic tourism revenue also reached a new high. In 2019,

the domestic tourism market continued to grow at a high speed. The annual total revenue reached 6.67 trillion yuan, an increase of 11.73% year-on-year, of which the cultural tourism industry accounted for 2.17 trillion yuan, accounting for 32.5%.

Statistics and growth of total revenue of China's tourism industry from 2012 to 2018

Data source: prepared by prospective industry research institute

At a time when China's cultural tourism industry is about to usher in vigorous development, the global COVID-19 broke out in 2020, and its potential spread to all regions of China. It also indirectly hit the developing cultural tourism industry, making the total revenue of the cultural tourism industry only 1.22 trillion in 2020, down 43.7% from 2018. However, according to the data of relevant institutions, the total revenue of China's cultural tourism industry has achieved a steady recovery after the epidemic in 2021, reaching 1.55 trillion yuan. In 2023, the total revenue of China's cultural tourism industry will exceed 2trillion yuan. It is predicted that the total revenue of China's cultural tourism industry will exceed 3trillion yuan in 2025, reaching 3.16 trillion yuan.

(3) The number of domestic tourists in China will exceed 8.5 billion in the future

According to the sampling survey results of domestic tourism, in 2017, the number of domestic tourists in China increased to more than 5billion, reaching 5.001 billion, a year-on-year increase of 12.8%. By 2018, the number of domestic tourists in China had reached 5.539 billion, a year-on-year increase of 10.8%, including 2.731 billion tourists in the cultural tourism industry. Especially with the launch of various tourism models with distinctive themes at the level of Chinese cultural tourism, The number of tourists participating in the cultural tourism industry will gradually increase. However, in 2020, affected by the epidemic, the number of tourists in China decreased briefly, and the specific data are not available. In 2021, only 700million people participated in the cultural tourism industry, which is the least in recent years. It can be seen that the epidemic has a great impact on the cultural tourism industry, and the number of people involved in tourism is also gradually decreasing. However, according to the statistical data from 2020 to the first half of 2022, the number of domestic tourists in China has obviously rebounded. The statistical data points out that the number of domestic cultural tourism participants in China will exceed 1.3 billion in 2022, and it is predicted that the number of domestic tourists in China will increase to about 2.7 billion in 2026, gradually returning to the level before 2019.

Statistics and forecast of the number of domestic cultural tourists in China from 2022 to 2026

Data source: prepared by prospective industry research institute

2.Problems Encountered In The Development Of Tourism Industry Under The Background Of Normalization Of Epidemic Prevention And Control

(1) Market aspect

1) Slow industrial recovery

In the face of the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, the main problem of China's cultural tourism industry in the market is the slow recovery of the cultural tourism industry. After the epidemic is gradually normalized for prevention and control, the cultural and tourism industry will also be reborn. However, due to the impact of the epidemic, most industries have temporarily stagnated, and restarting the development of the cultural and tourism industry is a long process, resulting in a slow recovery.

2) Reduction of industrial scale

The reduction of the scale of China's cultural tourism industry is the main reason for the slow development of the cultural tourism industry, and it is also one of the prominent problems in the cultural tourism industry market. The decrease in industrial scale is due to the continuous decrease in the number of subjects participating in the operation of the cultural tourism industry after the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, and the number of profitable subjects in the market is also decreasing, so the scale is far lower than that before the epidemic.

3) Prudent market capital flow

The flow of funds in the market determines the prosperity of the industry. However, due to the lack of profits in the cultural and tourism industry market under the epidemic prevention and control measures, there is a lack of government and enterprise investment, which makes some tourism industry funds unable to flow effectively to the cultural and tourism industry, and there is a lack of the main factor of market activity.

(2) Tourist Groups

1) Decrease In Consumption Proportion

After the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, the opportunities for tourism groups to participate in tourism will also change. The original number of participants in the tourism industry has decreased year by year after the outbreak, and the number of tourists participating in the cultural and tourism industry has not changed substantially. At this stage, the characteristic and problem is that the proportion of tourism consumption groups used for tourism has gradually decreased after the epidemic. On the one hand, the epidemic prevention and control can not achieve cross regional tourism. On the other hand, the epidemic has a very significant impact on the group's economic income, resulting in the reduction of the public's own disposable income. Therefore, the proportion of tourism consumption has also decreased.

2) Reduced Radiation Range

Before the epidemic, the domestic tourism of tourism groups in China's cultural tourism industry was mainly across provinces and cities. However, after the epidemic prevention and control, the prevention and control measures of different regions and the management policies of different provinces and cities for cross regional tourists are also different. As a result, tourists can only choose nearby tourist spots in the process of cultural tourism, and cannot carry out cross regional and cross provincial cultural tourism, This narrowing of tourism radiation is the reason for the epidemic prevention and control policy in the general environment.

3.) Increased psychological pressure

After the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, although the epidemic has basically achieved effective regional prevention and control, the public still has a very clear understanding of the epidemic. Some provinces are relatively strict in epidemic prevention and control, which leads to great psychological pressure on the public when traveling across regions. On the one hand, they are afraid of the spread of the COVID-19, on the other hand, they are afraid that they will be limited by the prevention and control measures when they are out of town, Therefore, such psychological pressure has led to a decline in the number of tourists participating in the cultural tourism industry.

(3) Enterprise Aspect

1) The degree of specialization of cultural tourism enterprises is reduced

The development of cultural tourism industry can not be separated from the participation of specialized cultural tourism enterprises, which has played a very important role in the market. After the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, the number of cultural and tourism enterprises has been decreasing. According to the data, the number of enterprises specializing in the cultural and tourism industry in 2018 has decreased by 42% by 2021. The main reason is that the original enterprises have abandoned their specialization in the cultural and tourism industry, resulting in a decrease in the number of enterprises. With the decrease of the number, the quality of cultural tourism provided by them is also declining, which eventually reduces the degree of specialization of cultural tourism enterprises.

2) The trend of innovative cultural tourism mode slows down

In 2018, as China put forward the concept of culture + tourism composite industry model, the Chinese tourism industry in the tourism industry has occupied a very important position, and its development speed has also increased year by year. Under such an environment, the cultural tourism industry has gradually realized self innovation, and the introduction of various models and concepts has enabled the cultural tourism industry to achieve new development. However, after the normalization of epidemic prevention and control measures, some enterprises abandoned the original idea of innovation and put forward a low-cost operation mode to survive the unstable period of cultural tourism industry development at this stage.

3) Brain drain of culture and tourism industry

Tourism enterprises involved in the cultural and tourism industry rely on strong capital operation and talent advantages to achieve competitiveness in the market. However, with the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, cultural and tourism enterprises have gradually reduced their investment and broadened their scope in the industrial development, resulting in the inability of some internal talents to obtain corresponding market benefits, so they try to participate in other industries, resulting in brain drain in the cultural and tourism industry, It has greatly damaged the development of the overall cultural and tourism industry. Talent is the foundation and core of industrial development. The cultural and tourism industry without talent participation will only show a backward situation, and can not achieve self upgrading and remodeling in difficulties.

(4) Government Policy

1) Difficulties in policy implementation

On the whole, the Chinese government has always maintained the concepts of policy guidance, capital investment, regional cooperation and cultural tourism resource sharing in supporting the development of the cultural tourism industry. However, most of the policy documents need specific implementers in practice, and the implementation of the policy is easy to conflict with the regional epidemic prevention measures, resulting in the original effective policy to solve the problem becoming a "high-altitude blueprint" that cannot be implemented. Such a situation is common in China at this stage. The difficulties in implementing the cultural tourism industry policy stem from different understandings and practices in different regions, as well as from epidemic prevention and control measures, so it leads to difficulties in implementing the policy.

2) The leading role of the government is not obvious

The development of cultural tourism industry needs not only the participation of enterprises, the public, funds and resources, but also the macro control of the government as a whole. At present, epidemic prevention and control is the most important work in China. The development of any industry must be unconditionally subject to the policies and measures for epidemic prevention and control. However, the cultural and tourism industry is an economic module in the work led by the government and needs to be consistent with the prevention and control measures in the region.

Therefore, some government policies and decisions in the cultural and tourism industry do not play an obvious role in practice and cannot form an effective driving force, So that the cultural tourism industry can realize reform and upgrading in the future development.

3)Reduction of capital investment in cultural tourism industry

After the outbreak of the COVID-19, it has greatly affected China's economic development, and the investment of funds in the market has also become very cautious due to the impact of the epidemic. The investment of limited funds in related fields has also been reduced, which is one of the problems after the normalization of epidemic prevention and control. The reduction of capital investment in the cultural and tourism industry is mainly due to the fact that the capital subjects in the market have become very cautious after being hit by investment, especially after the cultural and tourism industry has been affected by the epidemic, its operating status and market performance can not meet the minimum standards of investors, which leads to the reduction of investment.

3.Suggestions on the development of tourism industry against the background of normalization of epidemic prevention

(1) Stimulate market vitality and enhance profitability

The development of cultural tourism industry is inseparable from the stimulation of market vitality and the profitability of industrial subjects in the market. Therefore, this paper studies and analyzes the problems existing in the market in the development of tourism industry against the background of the normalization of epidemic prevention, and finds that the current development of cultural tourism industry needs to stimulate the vitality and power of the market, so as to enhance the profitability. First of all, under the background of normalization of epidemic prevention and control, as an important part of economic development, the cultural tourism industry is also driven by the development of China's tourism industry. It needs to quickly restore the industrial vitality, recall the market components that were gradually lost from the cultural tourism industry, and increase the ability to absorb capital from the surrounding industries and the market, so as to enable more industrial subjects to participate in the market competition, So as to stimulate market vitality. Secondly, to stimulate the market vitality, we need to increase the possibility of making profits in the market, effectively enhance the profitability, so that more cultural and tourism industry market players can gain profits in the cultural and tourism industry, so as to stimulate more players to participate. Only in this way can the cultural and tourism industry recover to the time before the outbreak of the epidemic. At the same time, we should also put forward new market operation methods in combination with the specific needs of prevention and control measures.

(2) Using scientific and technological means to diversify tourism modes

In addition to the main body of tourism development, the major participants in the tourism industry also include the group of tourists. Therefore, suggestions should be made for the tourism consumption group in combination with the concept of normalization of epidemic prevention and control. First of all, the modern tourism industry is not only a physical experience and feeling, but also a virtual acceptance of services. Therefore, we should create a diversified tourism mode and use scientific and technological means to enable more tourists to participate in different types of tourism, so as to realize the rapid development of the cultural tourism industry under the background of the normalization of epidemic prevention and control. Secondly, specifically speaking, the ways of multimedia and we media are relatively rich and effective, which can transform the physical activity of tourism into an online virtual activity. The cultural tourism industry itself includes the experience of the cultural concept and spirit of the tourism area. If VR video technology is adopted to enable the public to experience different customs around the world through mobile phones at home, combined with Internet of things technology and logistics technology, physical goods can be quickly delivered to tourists, realizing online consumption and offline experience of the cultural tourism industry, which greatly

stimulates the transformation of the cultural tourism industry itself. At the same time, it also reduces the pressure of repeated epidemics in the hearts of tourists, and basically realizes the purpose of cultural tourism. Finally, the diversified tourism mode is not only the realization of online tourism through scientific and technological means and the Internet, but also a necessary way for the development of the cultural tourism industry in the future. The combination of the Internet and we media makes the live broadcast and VR closer to reality, and shortens the distance between the world, which also enables the rapid spread of culture in space, free from space restrictions.

(3) Talent driven innovation to enhance the professionalism of the cultural tourism industry

The ultimate goal of enterprise development is not only to realize the social value of the enterprise, but also to obtain more benefits and funds. Under the background of normalization of epidemic prevention and control, cultural and tourism enterprises still need to rely on talents to maximize profits, and use talents to drive innovation, so as to improve the professionalism of cultural and tourism enterprises and realize the development of cultural and tourism industry. To effectively adjust the thinking mode of enterprise operation and change the traditional thinking of the original tourism enterprises, it is necessary to put forward innovative concepts through talents, and combine the characteristics of the enterprise to deal with the possible challenges and risks in the current market. The normalization of epidemic prevention and control shows that the development of any enterprise at this stage is inseparable from the premise of epidemic prevention and control. If the advantages of cultural and tourism enterprises rich in characteristics are used to put forward a more professional operation mode, for example, the purpose of red tourism is to enable the public to receive red patriotism education, it is necessary to strengthen the strength of cultural and tourism enterprises in transportation, medical treatment and personnel management in combination with epidemic prevention and control measures, Contact groups that need cultural tourism experience to take preventive and control measures in advance, and respond to emergencies with a professional attitude, so as to solve the problem of the reduction in the degree of specialization of the tourism industry under the background of the normalization of epidemic prevention and control. At the same time, to retain talents in the cultural and tourism industry, we need not only through salary and treatment, but also to provide an innovative platform for talents, so that they can use their own professional advantages to innovate the cultural and tourism model and quickly promote the innovation of cultural and tourism enterprises.

(4) Formulate practical policies to improve the profitability

As the driving force behind the development of the culture and tourism industry, the government and the country need to formulate pragmatic policies and guidelines, so as to improve the profitability of the culture and tourism industry in the market, so as to effectively solve the problems of policy implementation difficulties, the government's leading role is not obvious, and the reduction of capital investment in the culture and tourism industry. First of all, the government should flexibly formulate policies according to the actual situation of different regions and in combination with the local epidemic dynamics, delegate the power to provinces and cities, and put forward policies and measures in line with the local reality in combination with the normalization of local epidemic prevention and control and the development of the cultural and tourism industry, so as to promote the cultural and tourism industry. Secondly, the leading role of the government in the cultural and tourism industry is obvious, but under the background of the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, it is easy to lead to the gradual weakening of the effect. In particular, the implementation of some national cultural and tourism industry development guidance policies, different regions have different ways of implementation and combined epidemic prevention and control measures. Therefore, we should strengthen the supervision of policy guidance and practice, so that each measure can be implemented in line with local conditions. Finally, what the government needs to invest in the cultural tourism industry is that the cultural tourism industry can benefit rather than engage in "image engineering" and "political achievement Engineering". Each

investment of funds needs to obtain benefits and realize the further development of the industry, so as to effectively realize the income level of the cultural tourism industry through government policies.

Epilogue

The development of the cultural tourism industry in special periods will face special difficulties. At present, the normalization of epidemic prevention and control is a prerequisite for economic development and a high wall to prevent the tourism industry from moving forward quickly. Only by combining the normalization measures of epidemic prevention and control with the development of the cultural tourism industry, and by analyzing the specific current situation and future trend of the development of China's cultural tourism industry at this stage, Only in this way can we better find the problems faced by the cultural tourism industry in the development and put forward more consistent suggestions and measures. The development of China's cultural tourism industry is facing a critical period of industrial diversification, innovation, reform and upgrading. The author analyzes the problems of these factors in the context of the normalization of epidemic prevention and control from the perspective of bystanders, discusses them, puts forward suggestions and measures, and puts forward his own views and thoughts for the development of China's cultural tourism industry.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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